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journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/cepRecipe-based 1-D dynamic modeling of an integrated NH₃-synthesis-sorption reactorC. Sengoba^{*}, M. Illner, J.-U. Repke

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ABSTRACT

Long-term green hydrogen storage can be realized via flexible and efficient ammonia (NH₃) synthesis. Process intensification via a sorbent-integrated, ideally recycle-less NH₃-synthesis unit enables milder pressure and temperature levels during NH₃ synthesis, while shifting the single-pass conversion beyond the thermodynamic equilibrium. Understanding the process behavior of this novel, integrated synthesis-sorption reactor (SSR) requires an analysis and choice of suitable materials for catalysis and sorption based on the chemical equilibrium and kinetics of both the sorption and reaction phenomena. This study first proposes an equilibrium thermodynamic analysis to provide an initial performance assessment of a desired SSR, evaluating several sorbent material candidates. On this basis, a novel, pressure-driven dynamic model is developed to rigorously assess the inherently transient dynamics of a fixed-bed SSR in cyclic batch-wise operation under a predefined operation recipe. By consistent formulation of the conservation equations to describe the interplay of flow, reaction, and sorption phenomena, a physically accurate model is derived. Given the operation recipe, the simulation results highlight an NH₃ yield of 60.9%, substantially exceeding the single-pass conversion of 10–15%, typically achieved in state-of-the-art Haber–Bosch reactors. Additionally, a sensitivity analysis reveals that sorbent kinetics, rather than catalyst kinetics, should be the primary focus of material development to mitigate the effects of back-reaction in the presence of catalyst material during desorption. While the need for further material development is highlighted, this study provides the first rigorous dynamic evaluation of an integrated SSR for ammonia synthesis.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen (H₂) is a promising sustainable energy carrier and therefore hydrogen storage is a crucial building block for a sustainable energy economy. Especially in the electricity sector, long-term and large-scale storage capabilities are required to fulfill the European Green Deal mission [1,2].

The molecular properties of H₂ (e.g., density, diffusivity) however complicate transport and storage of molecular hydrogen, while chemical hydrogen storage in ammonia (NH₃), is a widely discussed alternative. The intermittent availability of renewable hydrogen requires a time-flexible storage process, whereas NH₃ is in turn an indispensable base chemical in various industries, mainly for nitrogen-based fertilizer production.

Conventional NH₃ production in large-scale Haber–Bosch (HB) reactors is typically energy-intensive and is operated at harsh operating conditions above 400 °C and 100 bar to achieve sufficient catalyst activity of state-of-the-art iron-based catalysts [3,4]. Given the rather low achievable single-pass hydrogen conversion of 10–15% [3,5], this

process typically involves a large recycle loop. Deploying ammonia as a long-term hydrogen carrier and storage however requires decentralized production and appropriate demand-side management (DSM), while simultaneously ensuring NH₃ supply at small scale, e.g., in remote areas.

Here, innovative approaches are required to enable resource-efficient H₂-storage via NH₃.

Numerous publications have suggested sorption-enhanced NH₃ synthesis for efficient and flexible NH₃ production to surpass the (thermodynamically limited) single-pass conversion performance of standard HB processes, e.g., [4,6–8]. The innovation essential to these proposed synthesis processes lies in the in-situ product (i.e. NH₃) separation to “shift” the thermodynamic synthesis equilibrium (cf. Section 2.1). At the same time, such a unit design concept can allow process flexibility, i.e. avoidance of a large recycle, and thus improved process dynamics and flexibility under milder conditions regarding operating temperature and pressure. From a process design perspective, sorption-enhanced synthesis can be realized in either a reactor along with a set of

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Nomenclature**Symbols**

μ	Gaseous phase viscosity, [kg (m s) ⁻¹]
λ_b	Axial thermal conductivity of the bed, [J (m K s) ⁻¹]
ν_i	Stoichiometric coefficient of species $i \in \text{N}_2, \text{H}_2, \text{NH}_3$
Δc_{H_2}	Change of H_2 concentration from I \rightarrow II, [mol m ⁻³]
Δc_{NH_3}	Change of NH_3 concentration from I \rightarrow II, [mol m ⁻³]
Δh_{298}^0	Reaction enthalpy at T = 298 K, [kJ mol ⁻¹]
Δh_R	Reaction enthalpy, [kJ mol ⁻¹]
Δh_S^0	Absorption enthalpy at T = 298 K, [kJ mol ⁻¹]
Δh_S	Absorption enthalpy, [kJ mol ⁻¹]
$\Delta h_{S,2-6}^0$	Absorption enthalpy at T = 298 K, [kJ mol ⁻¹]
Δs_S^0	Absorption entropy at T = 298 K, [J (mol K) ⁻¹]
$X_{\text{H}_2, I \rightarrow II}$	Theoretical H_2 -conversion assuming equilibria, [%]
ρ	Mass density, [kg m ⁻³]
ρ_i	Mass density of the i th species, [kg m ⁻³]
α_w	Wall heat transfer coefficient, [J (m ² K s) ⁻¹]
ϵ_S	Sorbent porosity [-]
ϵ_t	Total porosity [-]
ϵ_b	Bed porosity [-]
$-\nabla \cdot (\rho h v + q)$	Generalized volumetric enthalpy flux, [J (m ³ s) ⁻¹]
θ_{cat}	Catalyst to sorbent volumetric ratio, [-]
c	Total concentration, [mol m ⁻³]
c_i	Concentration of the i th species, [mol m ⁻³]
$D_{i,j}$	Binary diffusion coefficient, [m ² s ⁻¹]
$D_{m,i}$	Axial dispersion coefficient of the i th species, [m ² s ⁻¹]
d_P	Particle diameter, [m]
d_R	Reactor diameter, [m]
HU_V	Volumetric hold-up, [J (m ³ K) ⁻¹]
k	Kinetic rate coefficient, [kg (m ³ bar s) ⁻¹]
$k_{\text{abs}/\text{des}}$	Sorption rate coefficients, [mol _{NH₃} (m ³ bar s) ⁻¹]
K_a	Synthesis equilibrium constant, [-]
M_i	Molar weight of the i th species, [kg mol ⁻¹]
\bar{M}	Species-averaged molar weight, [kg mol ⁻¹]
p	Pressure, [bar]
p_0	Reference pressure, [Pa]
p_i	Partial pressure of the i th species, [bar]/[Pa]
$p_{\text{NH}_3, R-eg}$	NH_3 Synthesis equilibrium partial pressure, [bar]/[Pa]
$p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg}$	NH_3 Sorption equilibrium partial pressure, [bar]/[Pa]
R	Ideal gas constant, [J (mol K) ⁻¹] (8.3144)
$r_{R,i}$	Volumetric reaction rate of the i th species, [kg (m ³ s) ⁻¹]
$r_{S,i}$	Volumetric sorption rate of the i th species, [kg (m ³ s) ⁻¹]
$S_{\rho h}$	Generalized volumetric enthalpy source, [J (m ³ s) ⁻¹]
T	Temperature, [K]
T_w	Wall temperature, [K]
T_{in}	Inlet temperature, [K]
T_{eq}	Sorption-synthesis equilibrium temperature, [K]

separate absorber units (that operate in alternating modes, i.e. absorption/desorption modes) or a single integrated sorption-synthesis reactor (SSR) in cyclic quasi-steady-state operation. Both design concepts are

t	Time, [s]
t_{end}	Final time upon completion of the recipe, [s]
v	Velocity, [m s ⁻¹]
X	Sorbent relative load, [-]
X_{eq}	Extent of reaction at synthesis equilibrium, [-]
x_i	Mass fraction of the i th species, [-]
$\bar{x}_{\text{NH}_3, \text{out}}$	Time-averaged NH_3 purity at the outlet, [%]
Y_{NH_3}	NH_3 yield, [%]
$Y_{\text{NH}_3, R-eg}$	NH_3 -equilibrium yield, [%]
Z	Compressibility factor, [-]
z	Axial coordinate, [m]
Abbreviations and Acronyms	
DAE	Differential–algebraic equation system
DO	Dynamic optimization
DSM	Demand-side management
HB	Haber–Bosch
PDAE	Partial–differential–algebraic equation system
PDE	Partial-differential equation
SSR	Synthesis-sorption reactor

inherently transient and therefore require a dynamic model representation to capture the inherently cyclic absorption-desorption dynamics of the processes.

The present work focuses on developing a rigorous process model for the latter, namely a dead-end operation in a sorbent-integrated SSR in cyclic, dead-end operation. This decision is based on the goal of an increased residence time in the presence of an ammonia sorbent, thus favoring the desired sorption. To model the cyclical SSR operation, an operation recipe, i.e., time-varying boundary conditions, must be embedded in a dynamic process simulation. Further, the developed process model will be employed in a pilot-plant to support performance estimation via dynamic simulations in the near future [9].

Laboratory-scale investigations of the relevant sorption and synthesis kinetics at milder temperature and pressure conditions compared to those of state-of-the-art HB processes have already been carried out. For instance, Cholewa et al. [4] recently studied the kinetics of Ru-based catalysts (as well as Fe-based catalysts). Their experimental work aimed at an increased catalyst activity at low reaction temperatures (< 400 °C) and pressure conditions (< 100 bar) and hinted sorption-enhanced NH_3 synthesis.

Similarly, sorption-enhanced NH_3 synthesis has been investigated by Smith and Torrente-Murciano [7,10] to overcome the limitation imposed by the thermodynamic synthesis equilibrium.

In addition to experimental studies, several simulation studies have already been carried out on the subject of sorption-enhanced NH_3 synthesis.

For instance, a reactor unit along two separate absorber units was economically assessed in [8] in a simulation study, proving competitiveness with the traditional HB process at small production scales (≤ 6075 kg/h). Subsequent absorption/desorption experiments using MgCl_2 as a sorbent in [11] achieved a promising NH_3 product purity of over 72%. Both of these studies employed iron-based catalysts, which are standard for state-of-the-art industrial-scale Haber–Bosch processes.

A single, integrated SSR was previously modeled and analyzed using the analogy of a series of (flow) resistances to calculate achievable NH_3 -synthesis rates under various operation conditions spanning from $p = 25$ to 100 bar over different recycle ratios at $T = 400$ °C [10].

Later, Smith and Torrente-Murciano [7,12] developed a spatial model of an SSR. Their experimental set-up consisted of a layered unit with CeO_2 -supported Ru-catalyst and MnCl_2 absorbent layers operated at 20 bar. It was shown, that the equilibrium conversion of H_2 can be exceeded, particularly for temperatures < 350 °C. However, the

detailed phenomena in the reactor and the resulting limitations were not investigated.

The work of Malmali et al. [13] focuses on zero-dimensional models for absorption-enhanced low-pressure NH₃ production, comparing several catalyst kinetic models. Palys et al. [8] and Andres-Martinez et al. [14] have extended these models to flow-driven 1-D dynamic (i.e. PDE) models.

An experimental pilot-plant of layered, (i.e., integrated) ruthenium-based catalyst and MgCl₂-sorbent in [7] was modeled in a spatially discrete approach. Yet, this quasi-stationary approach apparently did not depict pressure losses as well as heat and mass transfer within the integrated unit.

A systematic assessment of the absorption equilibria (cf. Fig. 1) for sorption-enhanced NH₃ synthesis using a MgCl₂ sorbent has recently been presented by Kunz et al. [6]. However, a guided sorbent material selection regarding (operational) absorption and desorption pressure and temperature levels is still to be included into the design of an SSR.

Within the aforementioned contributions, the process models have not taken into account the molar defect due to simultaneous sorption/reaction in the respective conservation equations, leading to a potential model mismatch.

To address this research gap, the present work focuses on developing a rigorous process model for the dead-end (i.e., batch-wise) operation in a sorbent-integrated SSR. The goal of this recycle-less process design is to enable a high single-pass H₂-yield while achieving resource-efficiency and time-flexibility, i.e., fast process dynamics in the DSM context.

The conceptual process design of such a process involves the following hardly discussed questions, foremost regarding the working pairs of selectable catalyst and sorbent materials:

1. What is the theoretically achievable NH₃ yield considering the governing thermodynamic equilibria (i.e. absorption & synthesis equilibria)?
2. What are the performance limitations of an SSR during dynamic operation (p, T, absorption & catalyst kinetics performance windows)?
3. Can the performance of an SSR be increased via guided material development towards suitable ranges of absorption & catalyst kinetics?

To address the first question, we develop a thermodynamic equilibrium model for conversion performance assessment of an SSR.

Questions 2 and 3 are tackled by means of a dynamic simulation and subsequent sensitivity studies on selected model parameters of a novel 1-D spatial PDAE model formulated without implicit assumptions on the velocity field. This model represents a mandatory and novel extension, in the specific case of an SSR, where sorptive uptake leads to a substantial deviation from the continuity equation. Non-ideal thermodynamics for the equation of state and transport parameters are included to achieve a consistent and accurate model in a numerically favorable index-1 DAE formulation. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows:

Section 2 gives an overview of the thermodynamic models of reaction and metal halide absorption necessary to describe an SSR.

In Section 3, a sorbent material screening based on absorption equilibria indicates NiCl₂ as a promising sorbent material candidate. Thereon, a thermodynamic equilibrium-based assessment is presented in Section 3.2.1. This model is used to delimit the maximum achievable single-pass H₂-conversion rates in dynamic SSR operation based on the synthesis equilibrium and the sorption capacity.

The novel pressure-driven model is presented in Section 3.2.2, combined with an operation recipe for cyclic SSR operation. The purpose of this model is to map the performance limitations resulting from transport resistances and kinetics using rate-based submodels.

The case studies presented in Section 4 first show the simulation of a reference trajectory. Thereafter, sensitivity analyses are shown with

respect to operational and design parameters, and material-specific kinetic rate constants for both the sorbent and catalyst materials. These case studies provide insight into favorable operating windows and feasible combinations of sorbent and catalyst kinetics for an SSR. In turn, performance targets of the kinetics can be identified for material development for application in an SSR.

Section 5 concludes the findings of this investigation.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Synthesis and sorption thermodynamics

The performance of an SSR is thermodynamically limited by the sorption and synthesis equilibria. For NH₃ synthesis, the governing equilibrium reaction is stated as Eq. (1) (reaction enthalpy Δh_{298}^0 ; retrieved from [15]):

For ammonia adsorption on, e.g., zeolites, silica and activated carbon, it can be assumed that no viable working capacity can be achieved at temperatures > 300 °C. For example, adsorbent materials investigated already show a rapidly decreasing working capacity at $T > 150$ °C [16]. The influence of adsorption is therefore neglected for the remainder of this work.

The absorption equilibrium of a generic metal halide-NH₃ complex is given in Eq. (2) by An et al. [17] (corrected):

Describing the formation of several different (e.g., mono-, di-, hexamines) complexes within a metal halide species. Here, metal halide sorbent materials are specifically chosen due to their comparably high (chemi-)sorption capacity and being utilizable even at elevated temperatures. The state of thermodynamic equilibrium for this reaction is approximated via the Clapeyron equation (Eq. (3)):

$$\ln\left(\frac{p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg}}{p_0}\right) = -\frac{\Delta h_S^0}{RT} + \frac{\Delta s_S^0}{R} \quad (3)$$

Noteworthy, the thermal capacity of the involved materials may affect the validity of Eq. (3) far from standard conditions [17], which is however neglected in this work for the sake of simplicity.

2.2. Fixed-bed models for cyclic processes

Due to the conceptual similarity between an SSR and a standard PSA unit, the basis for model development in Section 3 are existing (spatial) dynamic PSA models, which are substantially extended:

Rota et al. [19] and Jee et al. [20] showed that PDE-constrained 1-D models can employ temporal boundary condition (BC) switching to represent pressure swing adsorption processes and pressure swing vacuum adsorption, respectively. Yet, many dynamic fixed-bed models involve unjustified assumptions and simplifications regarding the velocity field. This may lead to incorrect and at worst physically inconsistent model formulations, e.g.:

- A constant superficial velocity and thus implicitly neglecting the change in molar density, pressure and temperature
- The Ergun equation (Eq. (12)) combined with an assumed constant pressure in, e.g., [21]
- The assumption of an ideal gas behavior at high pressure levels (> 10 bar)

More specifically, a physical inconsistency arises in a model when the Ergun equation (Eq. (12)) and an equation of state model are combined under a constant (fixed) gas velocity. The inconsistency lies in the pressure field being determined by both (contradicting) aforementioned model equations.

(a) NH_3 partial pressure p_{NH_3} at synthesis equilibrium for different temperatures T . Synthesis equilibrium cf. [18].

(b) NH_3 -absorption equilibrium lines for several metal halide species, reproduced from [17]. $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_{2-6}\text{Cl}_2$ is denoted by Ni6-2 in the legend.

Fig. 1. Sorbent material equilibrium lines for different metal halide complexes. Based on [18], data cf. [17].

This represents a research gap regarding the accurate modeling of a physically consistent pressure-driven dynamic model formulation using a non-ideal equation of state model and boundary condition (BC) switching. However, such a model is essential for the modeling of dead-end absorption cycles and for application in the context of process development of a single-pass SSR.

3. Methods & model development

The aim of the models presented here is a thermodynamic characterization of a SSR in cyclic, dead-end operation and the identification of bottlenecks that arise during its dynamic operation.

To this end, a thermodynamic justification of the sorbent material choice of NiCl_2 is presented.

For this selected material, the expected yield performance is quantified considering the limiting thermodynamic equilibria. Subsequently, a 1-D dynamic model is presented to model the dynamic operation of an SSR. For this dynamic model, an operation recipe is implemented via temporal changes to the model boundary conditions. This recipe is used to model the cyclic SSR operation.

3.1. Sorbent material selection

A tailored sorbent selection takes into account the temperature and pressure levels during the synthesis/absorption step. For this purpose, (maximum) reactor inlet pressure of $p_{\text{H}} = 80$ bar and a temperature of $T = 573$ K during synthesis/sorption are assumed, i.e., milder conditions compared to state-of-the-art HB processes. On the other hand, sufficient catalyst activity is still expected for these conditions.

Given these conditions, the synthesis equilibrium partial pressure for a stoichiometric feed was calculated as $p_{\text{NH}_3, R-eg} = 38.80$ bar using Eq. (3) (Fig. 1(a)). A rather small partial pressure difference (i.e., $p_{\text{NH}_3, R-eg} - p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg}$) is believed to be desirable to prevent NH_3 back-reaction in the presence of the catalyst during the desorption step.

A sufficiently high partial pressure in the gaseous phase ($p_{\text{NH}_3, R-eg} > p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg}$) however is necessary as the driving force of the absorption step.

Given $p_{\text{NH}_3} = 38.80$ bar from Fig. 1(a) and $T = 573$ K, the $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_{2-6}\text{Cl}_2$ nickel chloride complex is identified as most promising candidate because the sorption equilibrium pressure ($p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} = 31.59$ bar in Fig. 1(b) [17]) is slightly lower than the synthesis equilibrium pressure $p_{\text{NH}_3, R-eg} = 38.80$ bar.

At first, full utilization of the sorbent's theoretical working capacity is assumed, disregarding kinetic limitations of sorption and synthesis as well as mass transfer limitations. This assumption will indeed lead to an over-estimation of the achievable NH_3 yield.

However, because of the lack of comparable sorption kinetics for the vast majority of metal halides studied, thermodynamic sorption equilibrium is used as a criterion for sorbent material selection. For the remainder of this contribution, NiCl_2 is thus set as the applied sorption material, in accordance with experimental studies carried out by Kubota et al. [22].

3.2. SSR mathematical model

With the NiCl_2 identified as a suitable sorbent material, two models for performance assessment of an SSR are introduced in the following.

First, a thermodynamic equilibrium-based model is provided in Section 3.2.1. This model is used to identify performance limitations due to thermodynamic equilibria of ammonia sorption and synthesis.

Secondly, the dynamic model described in Section 3.2.2 is employed to evaluate performance limitations that arise when reaction kinetics, sorption kinetics, and mass transfer are taken into account.

3.2.1. Thermodynamic assessment of SSR ammonia yield

The attainable yield of an SSR is thermodynamically limited by the synthesis equilibrium as well as the absorption equilibrium characterized by the specific (working) capacity. For the sorbent material, chemisorption must be considered, since NH_3 binds to $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2$ to form $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cl}_2$ according to Eq. (4).

Due to expected high operation temperatures, only the working capacities of metal halides are taken into account, i.e. the influence of support materials (e.g. zeolites, silica) on the equilibrium working capacity is neglected.

In this case, the absorption equilibrium can be modeled as a step-like absorption equilibrium for metal halides as reported in [13,23–25]. This is in line with assuming a sufficient ammonia partial pressure as a “cutoff criterion” of absorption (cf. [6]).

Hence, the absorption equilibrium is modeled in Eq. (5) as a conditional function of the current NH_3 partial pressure:

$$q = \begin{cases} q_{\text{NH}_3, \text{NiCl}_2, 2-6} & \text{if } p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} \leq p_{\text{NH}_3}, \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Physical adsorption on the sorbent surface is neglected for the remainder of this contribution, because only a negligible amount of ammonia adsorbate is expected, given the high temperatures required to achieve sufficient catalyst activity in the SSR. For the same reason, Co-adsorption of N_2 and/or H_2 is neglected.

The presented thermodynamic equilibrium model is based on an integral balance of two equilibrium system states (stoichiometric feed case):

Fully absorbed state: The void is filled with a gaseous mixture at synthesis equilibrium and sorbent is in sorption equilibrium for high pressure (p_{H}).

Fully desorbed state: The void is filled with the same composition as in the absorbed state (i.e. no back reaction in the presence of the catalyst) and the sorbent is in equilibrium for low pressure (p_{L}).

(a) Sensitivity of the theoretical NH_3 yield Y_{NH_3} to the extent of reaction reached (fraction of the equilibrium conversion); calculated according to Eq. (6).

(b) Sensitivity of the theoretical NH_3 yield Y_{NH_3} to sorbent working capacity (as a fraction of the stoichiometric maximum possible sorbent working capacity); calculated according to Eq. (6).

Fig. 2. Sensitivity graphs of Y_{NH_3} for varied reaction extents X_{eq} & sorbent working capacities q_{NiCl_2} (isothermal temperature $T = 573$ K in all cases).

The assumptions behind this thermodynamic equilibrium model are:

1. No back-reaction in the presence of the catalyst, no product retention.
2. In the examined pressure regime (p_{NH_3}) only the di-amine to hex-amine complex forms (Eq. (4)).
3. Catalyst volume is negligible, $\varepsilon_S = 0.6$.
4. Neglecting the limitations imposed by mass transfer & catalyst/sorbent kinetics.
5. The gaseous mixture in the void is described by the Soave-Redlich-Kwong equation of state (using the AmsterCHEM library [26]) and the thermodynamic synthesis equilibrium according to [27].

Given the (ideal) assumptions stated above, the maximum achievable NH_3 -yield is formulated by Eq. (6) as a primary performance metric. This equation stems from the integral mass balance for the transition between the fully absorbed and fully desorbed states. A detailed derivation of $Y_{\text{NH}_3, \text{Abs.} \rightarrow \text{Des.}}$ is provided in the Supplementary Information.

$$Y_{\text{NH}_3, \text{Abs.} \rightarrow \text{Des.}} = 1 - \frac{\Delta c_{\text{out}, \text{H}_2, \text{Abs.} \rightarrow \text{Des.}}}{\Delta c_{\text{in}, \text{H}_2, \text{Abs.} \rightarrow \text{Des.}}} \quad (6)$$

First, the influence of catalyst performance on the SSR performance is to be investigated. For this purpose, it is assumed that a lower catalyst activity leads to a proportionally lower synthesis conversion relative to the synthesis equilibrium conversion. This determines the sensitivity of the achievable NH_3 yield regarding catalyst performance. Fig. 2(a) shows the theoretically achievable NH_3 yield for different extents of the synthesis equilibrium under variable system pressure p . Jumps can be recognized at certain system pressure p levels, which correspond to exceeding the sufficient ammonia partial pressure for absorption.

Secondly, the sensitivity of the NH_3 yield with regard to sorbent working capacity is quantified. Fig. 2(b) displays theoretically achievable NH_3 yield for varying sorbent capacities q_{NiCl_2} under variable pressure p .

Here, analogous jumps can be recognized as in Fig. 2(a). An NH_3 yield $> 90\%$ is achievable from this thermodynamic equilibrium point-of-view, given the stated idealized assumptions. Even assuming that the synthesis equilibrium is not fully achieved (Fig. 2(a)) or that the sorption capacity cannot be fully utilized (Fig. 2(b)), a high NH_3 yield $> 90\%$ is thermodynamically achievable.

3.2.2. 1-D dynamic SSR model

To analyze the performance limitations introduced by reaction kinetics, absorption kinetics, and mass transfer when assessing the achievable conversion, a dynamic reactor model is developed. A (spatially resolved) 1-D pseudo-homogeneous dynamic model of a tubular reactor, i.e. partial-differential-algebraic equation system (PDAE), is provided to describe the reactor unit's dynamic operation.

This dynamic model is based on a first-principles approach, with the following assumptions:

1. Negligible radial gradients ($\frac{\partial}{\partial r} = 0$), due to a small tube diameter ($d_R = 0.025$ m) relative to the reactor length of $L = 0.5$ m.
2. The heat flux across the reactor wall is modeled using a volumetric source term.
3. For a pressure-driven approach, the axial momentum conservation according to the Ergun equation (Eq. (12)) is deployed.
4. Constant wall temperature T_w .
5. No use of sweep gas (i.e. zero flushing) as the desorption is realized purely by lowering the system pressure.

The reactor dimensions were estimated based on a model of a pilot-plant currently under construction [28]. Eq. (7) denotes the differential component balance:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial t} = -v \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial z} - \rho_i \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} + D_{m,i} \frac{\partial^2 \rho_i}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1 - \varepsilon_b}{\varepsilon_b} (\theta_{\text{cat}} r_{R,i} + (1 - \theta_{\text{cat}}) r_{S,i}) \quad (7)$$

The axial dispersion coefficient $D_{m,i}$ is calculated via a correlation for fixed-bed models adopted from [29]. The binary gas-phase diffusion coefficients are calculated using a predictive model by Fuller et al. [30] in Multiflash™. The bed porosity is assumed as $\varepsilon_b = 0.6$, according to Palys et al. [8].

The volumetric energy balance equation (Eq. (8)) balances the generalized fluxes and source terms:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{HU_{\rho h}} (-\nabla(\rho h v + q) + S_{\rho h}) \quad (8)$$

In the energy balance, the hold-up $HU_{\rho h}$ is as follows (Eq. (9)):

$$HU_{\rho h} = \varepsilon_b \rho c_{p,g} + (1 - \varepsilon_b) \rho_S c_{p,s} \quad (9)$$

to account for the solid and gas phase volumetric heat capacities. Eq. (10) defines the generalized flux (i.e. convective and diffusive flux) in axial direction:

$$-\nabla(\rho h v + q) = -\varepsilon_b c_{p,g} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho v T) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\lambda_b \frac{\partial T}{\partial z}). \quad (10)$$

The source term $S_{\rho h}$ is the sum of the enthalpy source associated with sorption and transport over the reactor wall (Eq. (11)):

$$S_{\rho h} = (1 - \varepsilon_b)(1 - \theta_{\text{cat}}) \Delta h_S r_{S, \text{NH}_3} + (1 - \varepsilon_b) \theta_{\text{cat}} (-\Delta h_R) r_{R, \text{NH}_3} + \frac{4 \alpha_w}{d_R} (T_w - T) \quad (11)$$

The heat transfer coefficient of the wall α_w and the thermal conductivity of the bed λ_b are calculated according to correlations from [31, 32], respectively. The gas velocity field is calculated using the Ergun

Table 1
PDAE reactor model parameters.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Description
α	0.64	[-]	Kinetic rate model constant
ω	1.564	[-]	Kinetic rate model constant
μ	2.586×10^{-5}	$[\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}]$	Gas dynamic viscosity
θ_{cat}	0.5	[-]	Catalyst to sorbent proportion
ρ_S	355.0	$[\text{kg m}^{-3}]$	Sorbent density
d_p	1.0×10^{-3}	[m]	Sorbent particle diameter
d_R	2.5×10^{-2}	[m]	Reactor diameter
E_{abs}	24.7×10^3	$[\text{J mol}^{-1}]$	Activation energy (Abs.); cf. [22]
E_{des}	50.5×10^3	$[\text{J mol}^{-1}]$	Activation energy (Des.); cf. [22]
L	0.5	[m]	Reactor length
p_H	80.0	[bar]	maximum inlet pressure
q_{eq}	147.8	$[\text{kg m}^{-3}]$	Volumetric sorbent NH_3 -load (eq.)
T_{in}	573	[K]	Inlet temperature
T_w	573	[K]	Wall temperature

equation (Eq. (12)), i.e., a simplified momentum balance equation [8]:

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = \frac{150(1 - \varepsilon_b)^2 \mu}{\varepsilon_b^3 d_p^2} v + \frac{1.75(1 - \varepsilon_b)}{\varepsilon_b^2 d_p} \rho |v| v \quad (12)$$

To calculate the total system pressure, a compressibility factor-corrected ideal gas law is formulated in Eq. (13). Thus, the equation of state employed in the model remains exchangeable:

$$p = \frac{\rho}{M} RT Z(T, p, x_i) \quad (13)$$

The Soave-Redlich-Kwong equation of state is used to calculate $Z(T, p, x_i)$. Notably, Eq. (13) is an implicit function for p w.r.t. T, x_i .

The rate equations for reaction kinetics in Eq. (14) are adopted from [27], depending on the equilibrium constant K_a . The catalyst efficiency factor η_{cat} is according to [8].

$$r_{R,i=\text{NH}_3} = M_{\text{NH}_3} \eta_{cat} k_R \left[K_a^2 a_{\text{N}_2} \left(\frac{a_{\text{H}_2}^{3/2}}{a_{\text{NH}_3}} \right) - \frac{a_{\text{NH}_3}}{a_{\text{H}_2}^{3/2}} \right] \quad (14)$$

in which the activities a_i are simplified to the partial pressures p_i , i.e., $\gamma_i = 1$ for all 3 components, assuming ideal behavior of the involved reactant molecules on the catalyst surface. An experimentally validated sorption rate model for the NiCl_2 complex ((4)) is adopted from [22]. The absorption rate coefficient is conditioned on the relative load X (also denoted as ‘‘sorption conversion’’) and NH_3 partial pressure p_{NH_3} (Eq. (15)):

$$k_{abs} = \begin{cases} 4.85 \exp\left(\frac{-E_{abs}}{RT}\right) & \text{if } (X < 1 \wedge p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} < p_{\text{NH}_3}), \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

whereas the analogous Eq. (16) denotes the desorption coefficient:

$$k_{des} = \begin{cases} -3.80 \times 10^4 \exp\left(\frac{-E_{des}}{RT}\right) & \text{if } (X > 0 \wedge p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} > p_{\text{NH}_3}), \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Thus, absorption can only take place if the sorbent is not fully charged ($X < 1$) and a sufficient driving force is fulfilled ($p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} < p_{\text{NH}_3}$). Similarly, desorption can only occur if the sorbent load is above zero ($X > 0$) and $p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} > p_{\text{NH}_3}$ holds.

The coefficients are then applied in the sorption model to describe both absorption and desorption in the rate equation, as expressed in Eq. (17):

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = (k_{abs} + k_{des})(1 - X)^{2/3} (|p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} - p_{\text{NH}_3}|)^n \quad (17)$$

and the accumulation term for absorbent load is (Eq. (18)):

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = -r_{S, \text{NH}_3} = q_{eq} (k_{abs} + k_{des})(1 - X)^{2/3} (|p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} - p_{\text{NH}_3}|)^n \quad (18)$$

The defined model parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 2

Recipe schedule, structure adapted from [33]. A detailed overview over the dynamic BC switching is given in Table A.4 in Appendix A. For equilibration at 20 bar (step 14), the operation recipe ends with a wait time of 60 s.

Step	Type	Description
1	step	open inlet valve
2	ramp	ramp up inlet pressure p_{in} at 0.05 bar/s
3	condition	wait until $p_{in} = p_H$ is reached
4	set	hold p_{in}
5	condition	wait for 3600 s
6	set	$p_{out} = p _{z=L}$
7	step	close inlet valve & open outlet valve
8	ramp	ramp down outlet pressure p_{out} at -0.05 bar/s
9	condition	wait until $p_{out} \leq 20$ bar
10	set	hold p_{out}
11	condition	wait until $p _{x=0} \leq p_{out} + 0.05$ bar
12	step	close outlet valve
13	set	set inlet pressure to current system pressure $p_{in} = p _{z=0}$
14	condition	wait for 60 s
15	END	

3.2.3. Recipe formulation for boundary condition switching

The operation of an SSR is inherently cyclic, characterized by the following steps: *Pressure build-up*, *Reaction/ Absorption*, *Depressurization* and *Desorption*. With the PDAE system at hand, the temporal changes of the boundary conditions that correspond to these steps are to be formulated accordingly.

Temporal switching of BCs based on transition conditions can be formalized using an operation recipe formulation as proposed by Brand-Rihm et al. [33]. An operation recipe serves as a parametrization of the control space using time-invariant recipe parameters (cf. [33]), which comes at the cost of a restricted control space. Thus, such an operation recipe formulation increases the convergence behavior of dynamic simulations. The BCs for different modes during the operation cycle are adjusted periodically [21,34].

The operation recipe employed in this work is shown in Table 2 along with its recipe steps and transition conditions. Note that the listed BCs include u and p on the boundary of spatial the domain $z = [0, L]$. As the discretization scheme (Section 3.3) requires values for both of these algebraic values on the boundary, additional modeling equations are needed. These 2 variables, along with the variables ρ_i require BCs categorized as time-variant (based on the aforementioned operation recipe) and time-invariant, the latter being described in Section 3.2.4.

At the inlet ($z = 0$), the gas velocity v is calculated via the Ergun equation (Eq. (12)) during steps 1–7 of the operation recipe, while it is set to $v|_{z=0} = 0$ for steps 8–14 and vice versa at the outlet ($z = L$). $p|_{z=0}$ is switched from the set parameter p_{in} (during steps 1–7) to a calculated variable using the equation of state (Eq. (13)) during steps 8–14.

3.2.4. Time-invariant boundary conditions

During every step of the operation recipe the BCs on $\rho_i|_{z=0}$ are governed by the Danckwert’s BC, which defines a balance of fluxes at the inlet ($z = 0$). The influx of mass of component i $\rho_i|_{z=0} v|_{z=0}$ is the inlet flux $\rho_{in,i} v|_{z=0}$ minus a term to account for the dispersive backmixing of i (Eq. (19)):

$$D_{m,i} \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=0} + v|_{z=0} (\rho_{in,i} - \rho_i|_{z=0}) = 0 \quad (19)$$

At the reactor outlet ($z = L$) on the other hand, the BC on $\rho_i|_{z=L}$ is set by a Neumann BC (zero-gradient):

$$\frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=L} = 0 \quad (20)$$

The analogous boundary conditions for the energy balance are defined by Eq. (21) for the temperature T :

$$\lambda_b \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=0} + \rho c_{p,s} v|_{z=0} (T_{in} - T|_{z=0}) = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right|_{z=L} = 0 \quad (22)$$

The inlet species densities are specified implicitly in Eq. (23) for a set inlet pressure p_{in} and N_2 - H_2 stoichiometric ratio of the inlet gas mixture as:

$$\lambda_{in} = \frac{\frac{\rho_{in,i=N_2}}{M_{N_2} \nu_{N_2}}}{\frac{\rho_{in,i=H_2}}{M_{N_2} \nu_{N_2}}} \quad (23)$$

combined with the equation of state (Eq. (13)). The pressure p at the spatial domain's right-hand boundary ($x = L$) is a control variable.

3.2.5. Performance metrics

The NH_3 yield and the time-averaged outlet NH_3 purity (along with productivity), as stated in [21], serve as the performance metrics to benchmark the SSR against a state-of-the-art HB reactor. Both criteria are evaluated over the complete operation cycle (i.e.: $*_{i_0} = *_{i_{end}}$). The NH_3 yield is described by Eq. (24), while the time-averaged NH_3 purity at the outlet is described by Eq. (25). The productivity (in relation to catalyst mass) is defined by Eq. (26).

$$Y_{NH_3} = \frac{\int_0^{t_{end}} c_{NH_3} v_{z=L} dt | v_{NH_3}}{\int_0^{t_{end}} c_{H_2} v_{z=0} dt v_{H_2}} \quad (24)$$

$$\bar{x}_{NH_3,out} = \frac{\int_0^{t_{end}} c_{NH_3} v_{z=L} dt}{\int_0^{t_{end}} c v_{z=L} dt} \quad (25)$$

$$Productivity_{NH_3} = \frac{\int_0^{t_{end}} c_{NH_3} v_{z=L} dt}{L \rho_{cat} \Delta t_{end}} \quad (26)$$

3.3. Spatial discretization & recipe implementation

An orthogonal collocation on finite elements (OCFE) with a second order basis is applied, to spatially discretize the developed PDAE (Eqs. (7)–(23)). The spatial domain is thus discretized into 100 finite elements of equal length, according to a grid independence study.

The numerical solution including the operation recipe is carried out in gPROMS[®] through the SEQUENCE command [35] to implement the conditional statements listed in Table 2. Within gPROMS[®] the Multiflash[™] physical property interface is internally called to calculate the compressibility factor Z , the binary interaction parameters $D_{i,j}$ to calculate $D_{m,i}$, the gaseous phase heat capacities $c_{p,g}$, and the parameters necessary to calculate axial thermal conductivity λ_b [36]. All simulations are performed on an Intel[®] Core[™] i7-10700 CPU @ 2.90 GHz/16.0 GB RAM machine running 64-bit Windows 10 Education.

4. Simulation results

The developed model (Eqs. (7)–(25)) was applied in a reference case simulation, that employs absorption characteristics and catalyst kinetics from literature, using the parameters described in Table 1. The sorbent-to-catalyst volumetric ratio is arbitrarily set to $\theta_{cat} = 0.5$, while the feed stoichiometric ratio of the inlet is set to $\lambda_{in} = 1$. The recipe parameters applied in the reference case simulation are listed in Table 1.

4.1. Reference case simulation results

The overall mass-balance of the reactor over the operation recipe was solved to a relative accuracy ($\epsilon_{rel} < 4 \times 10^{-5}$) for the reference case simulation indicating an acceptable discretization error of the spatial OCFE discretization scheme. The computation time of on simulation was typically ≈ 300 s.

Upon completion of the operation recipe at $t_{end} = 6071$ s, the resulting performance metrics of $Y_{NH_3} = 60.9\%$ and $\bar{x}_{NH_3,out} = 43.8\%$ are considerably higher than in a conventional Haber–Bosch reactor.

Fig. 3. Temperature trajectory $T(t, z)$ ($p_H = 80$ bar, $T_W = T_{in} = 573$ K, $\lambda_{in} = 1.0$).

Fig. 4. NH_3 -synthesis rate $r_{R,NH_3}(t, z)$ trajectory ($p_H = 80$ bar, $T_W = T_{in} = 573$ K, $\lambda_{in} = 1.0$).

However, the calculated NH_3 yield is still lower than the synthesis equilibrium yield of $Y_{NH_3,R-eq} = 65.3\%$.

The productivity of a complete operation cycle in the reference case is $0.97 \text{ mol}_{NH_3}/\text{kg}_{cat}/\text{h}$. This is an increase compared to the productivity reported in lab-scale SSR experiments by Smith and Torrente-Murciano [7] ($\approx 0.08 \text{ mol}_{NH_3}/\text{kg}_{cat}/\text{h}$, assuming an even sorbent-to-catalyst volumetric ratio and $\epsilon_{bed} = 0.4$ at ≈ 573 K), which makes the case for the dead-end operation mode. On the contrary, traditional HB process operation conditions allow a for substantially higher NH_3 -synthesis productivity, e.g., $48.6 \text{ mol}_{NH_3}/\text{kg}_{cat}/\text{h}$ at 90 bar and 648 K, reported by Nadiri et al. [37]. This must be weighed against the advantages of milder operating conditions in the SSR.

4.1.1. Reference case trajectories

Figs. 3–7 show the trajectories of selected variables in the reference case simulation for 5 equidistant positions along the spatial coordinate z .

Fig. 3 depicts the trajectories of the local temperature T . In the beginning of recipe step 3 (i.e. *Pressurization*) an initial peak in temperature is apparent due to exothermic NH_3 formation. Once the inlet pressure reaches the predefined maximum p_H (Step 5) the temperature settles on the wall temperature T_w , except at the inlet ($z = 0$), which can be explained by slow feed replenishment and quasi-stationary (exothermic) ammonia formation near the inlet. In contrast, further along the axial direction, the synthesis reaction is at equilibrium as the local reaction rate r_{R,NH_3} is near zero.

As the opening states switch and the outlet pressure begins to decrease, a temperature drop due to endothermic desorption is enforced. After the desorption step (i.e. end of recipe step 14) the temperature settles back to T_w across the unit.

Accordingly, the NH_3 -synthesis rate trajectory (shown in Fig. 4) indicates an initial peak that begins with recipe step 3. Subsequently, slow quasi-stationary NH_3 formation close to $z = 0$ due to feed

Fig. 5. Absorbent volumetric NH_3 load $q(t, z)$ ($p_H = 80$ bar, $T_W = T_{in} = 573$ K, $\lambda_{in} = 1.0$).

replenishment is visible during step 5. Once the outlet pressure is ramped down, a small negative NH_3 -synthesis rate, i.e. NH_3 cracking occurs due to depressurization.

The sorbent load trajectory is shown in Fig. 5. As the sorbent load reaches zero, an abrupt end of the desorption leads to small positive peaks in the NH_3 -synthesis rate. The trajectory highlights that q significantly falls short of the maximum sorption capacity q_{max} in every axial position over operation recipe. This is because the NH_3 absorption reduces the local p_{NH_3} that serves as the driving force of the sorption itself (Eq. (17)). Thus, r_{S, NH_3} is effectively self-stabilized at a rather slow rate, given a driving pressure difference of $p_{\text{NH}_3} - p_{\text{NH}_3, S-eg} \approx 0.1$ bar. Moreover, there is practically no NH_3 absorption close to the inlet, due to the elevated temperature (Fig. 3), see also Eq. (3).

In Fig. 6 the trajectories of the partial pressure of all three components show a steep increase beginning with recipe step 3. Both p_{N_2} and p_{H_2} (Figures Fig. 6(a) and (b)) show a peak after the predefined maximum pressure p_H is reached, indicating diffusive fluxes of both components along the axial direction. These peaks at the reactor inlet ($z = 0$) settle once the inlet pressure reaches its maximum during recipe step 5. However, a peak at the inlet of the N_2 -partial pressure p_{N_2} and the H_2 -partial pressure p_{H_2} remains throughout the Reaction/Absorption steps, namely until step 9 of the defined recipe (Table 2) is reached. In turn, p_{NH_3} (Fig. 6(c)) shows an axial increase between $z = 0 - 0.25 L$. This increase is due to only a trace amount of NH_3 entering the SSR, and the resulting dispersive back-mixing effect is correspondingly pronounced. This further emphasizes the observed quasi-stationary formation of NH_3 near the inlet, i.e. $z = 0 - 0.25 L$ (cf. Figs. 3 and 4).

With a pressure-driven formulation applied, velocity fields, as shown in Fig. 7 are obtained. Given the operation schedule, physically sound profiles are obtained especially at the inlet and outlet, where the velocity is $u = 0$ for the respective recipe state (i.e. no flow at the outlet for the Reaction/Absorption steps; no flow at the inlet for the Desorption steps.)

While the sorption kinetics and the described negative interaction between sorption and reaction phenomena remain a principal obstacle, an appropriate choice of design measures (Fig. 8) can lead to an increased NH_3 yield.

4.2. Sensitivity analyses

To quantify the influence of control variables and material-specific parameters on the NH_3 yield Y_{NH_3} , a sensitivity study is conducted. Therein, the selection of varied model parameters is categorized into operational/design parameters (λ_{in} , T_W , and θ_{cat}) and kinetic rate constants (Eq. (14) & Eq. (17)). A potential performance increase in the latter is an object of study in the context of material development. The colormap plots shown in Figs. Figs. 8 and 9 are based on converged simulations (marked by \times) that were subsequently interpolated via linear interpolation.

(a) N_2 partial pressure trajectory $p_{\text{N}_2}(t, z)$.

(b) H_2 partial pressure trajectory $p_{\text{H}_2}(t, z)$.

(c) NH_3 partial pressure trajectory $p_{\text{NH}_3}(t, z)$.

Fig. 6. Species partial pressure ($p_i(t, z)$) trajectories ($p_H = 80$ bar, $T_W = T_{in} = 573$ K, $\lambda_{in} = 1.0$).

Fig. 7. Gas velocity $u(t, z)$ trajectory ($p_H = 80$ bar, $T_W = T_{in} = 573$ K, $\lambda_{in} = 1.0$).

Fig. 8. Sensitivity graphs for varied catalyst/sorbent volumetric ratios θ_{cat} and a uniform inlet/reactor wall temperature $T_W (= T_{in})$; (a): excess of H_2 ($\lambda_{in} = 0.5$), (b): stoichiometric feed mixture ($\lambda_{in} = 1.0$), (c): excess of N_2 ($\lambda_{in} = 1.5$). All converged simulations are marked by \times . The vertical lines mark the respective theoretical sorption-synthesis equilibrium temperature T_{eq} .

4.2.1. Design & operational parameters

The 3 different sensitivity graphs displayed in Fig. 8 show Y_{NH_3} for varied catalyst-to-sorbent volumetric ratios θ_{cat} and varied wall/inlet temperatures (assuming setpoints that fulfill $T_W = T_{in}$) under three different cases for the inlet stoichiometric ratio λ_{in} . In each of the three graphs, a (hypothetical) equilibrium temperature T_{eq} is marked vertically. This temperature marks the intersection of NH_3 sorption and synthesis equilibria for a given feed mixture. In practical terms, no interplay of sorption and synthesis is possible at temperatures exceeding T_{eq} .

The highest calculated value Y_{NH_3} of 67.7% is reached at $T_W = 564$ K and $\theta_{cat} = 10\%$, before a sharp decrease in Y_{NH_3} w.r.t. temperature in case of N_2 -excess ($\lambda_{in} = 1.5$) becomes apparent. In all cases, a lower θ_{cat} (i.e. higher volumetric share of absorbent material) leads to an increased NH_3 yield. This increase can be attributed to an increased amount of product NH_3 absorbed over on operation cycle, which indicates potential for optimization. At the same time, the productivity is indeed increased to $2.65 \text{ mol}_{NH_3}/\text{kg}_{cat}/\text{h}$, which further indicates that the NH_3 -synthesis rate is not limiting the SSR performance given the defined recipe.

Also, a higher inlet/wall temperature leads to an increased NH_3 yield up until a temperature level that appears to be independent of all 3 varied parameters and corresponds to a p_{NH_3} in the reactor that is insufficient to match the absorption equilibrium pressure (Eq. (3)). This limit routes back to the step-like sorption behavior represented by Eq. (5). The increase in Y_{NH_3} before reaching this temperature level may neither be explained by an improved mass transfer, nor

Fig. 9. NH_3 yield sensitivity Y_{NH_3} w.r.t. kinetic rate constants. All converged simulations are marked by \times .

through the synthesis equilibrium (Eq. (1)), which indeed favors a lower temperature. Instead, a higher ammonia partial pressure p_{NH_3} in the void is detrimental to the overall NH_3 yield, comparable to the lower NH_3 yield rates at higher maximum pressures shown in Fig. 2.

4.2.2. Catalyst & sorbent kinetic rate parameters

To shed light on the influence of the underlying kinetic rate models of the reaction and the sorption phenomena, the respective rate constants are varied. Here, a maximum two-fold increase in the kinetic rates through the development of catalyst/sorbent materials was considered realistic. Therefore, the sensitivity in a range of -80 to $+100\%$, respectively, is examined.

As shown in Fig. 9, there is a slight decrease of Y_{NH_3} with an increased catalyst kinetic rate constant k_0 , which is explainable as NH_3 back-reaction in the presence of the catalyst occurring and thereby reducing the overall conversion. In contrast, faster sorption kinetics show an increase in Y_{NH_3} , with an impact comparable to that of θ_{cat} . The increased Y_{NH_3} for faster sorption kinetics can be attributed to a lower time window for back-reaction in the presence of the catalyst to occur during the (pressure-driven) desorption. Essentially, the conducted sensitivity analyses show that:

- The achieved NH_3 yield of $Y_{NH_3} = 60.9\%$ (and likewise H_2 -single-pass conversion) exceeds the yield achieved in traditional Haber–Bosch reactors (10–15%)
- A N_2 -excess in the feed ($\lambda_{in} = 1.5$) leads to higher NH_3 yields at the cost of increased recycle streams
- Realizing this maximum achievable NH_3 yield requires a temperature set point well below the calculated equilibrium temperature ($T_W \approx T_{eq} - 10$ K)
- A high relative sorbent volume fraction of 90% leads to an increased NH_3 yield

5. Conclusion

In this work, the performance of sorption-enhanced ammonia synthesis, i.e., the integration of NH_3 synthesis and sorption in a single unit, has been theoretically investigated. To this end, an operation recipe for a dead-end cyclic operation mode of a synthesis-sorption reactor (SSR) was defined. First, the thermodynamic equilibria of different metal halide/ammonia complex pairs were compared. From this, $NiCl_2$ was selected as a suitable sorbent material under predefined temperature and pressure conditions.

Two models were subsequently presented, depicting (a) limitations due to thermodynamic equilibria of absorption and synthesis over a complete cycle and (b) under dynamic SSR operation in a novel, recipe-based, pressure-driven dynamic model. The prior model showed a theoretically achievable NH_3 yield $> 90\%$ even under kinetic limitation

Table A.4
Temporally switched and time-invariant boundary conditions in the operation recipe (as stated in Table 2).

Step	T		ρ_i		u		p	
	$x = 0$	$x = L$						
1					Eq. (12) _{z=0}	$u _{z=L} = 0$	$p _{z=0} = p_{in}$	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
2					Eq. (12) _{z=0}	$u _{z=L} = 0$	$p _{z=0} = p_{in}$	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
3					Eq. (12) _{z=0}	$u _{z=L} = 0$	$p _{z=0} = p_{in}$	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
4					Eq. (12) _{z=0}	$u _{z=L} = 0$	$p _{z=0} = p_{in}$	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
5					Eq. (12) _{z=0}	$u _{z=L} = 0$	$p _{z=0} = p_{in}$	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
6					Eq. (12) _{z=0}	$u _{z=L} = 0$	$p _{z=0} = p_{in}$	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
7					$u _{z=0} = 0$	Eq. (12) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	$p _{z=L} = p_{out}$
8	Eq. (21) _{z=0}	Eq. (22) _{z=0}	Eq. (19) _{z=0}	Eq. (20) _{z=0}	$u _{z=0} = 0$	Eq. (12) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	$p _{z=L} = p_{out}$
9					$u _{z=0} = 0$	Eq. (12) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	$p _{z=L} = p_{out}$
10					$u _{z=0} = 0$	Eq. (12) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	$p _{z=L} = p_{out}$
11					$u _{z=0} = 0$	Eq. (12) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	$p _{z=L} = p_{out}$
12					$u _{z=0} = 0$	$u _{z=L} = 0$	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
13					$u _{z=0} = 0$	$u _{z=L} = 0$	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
14					$u _{z=0} = 0$	$u _{z=L} = 0$	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=L}
15					$u _{z=0} = 0$	$u _{z=L} = 0$	Eq. (13) _{z=0}	Eq. (13) _{z=L}

of the NH₃ synthesis or partial sorbent load, which underlines the viability of the promising integrated sorption-synthesis process. Using the latter model, a reference case simulation resulted in an NH₃ yield ($Y_{NH_3} = 60.9\%$) well beyond the synthesis equilibrium conversion. In contrast, the productivity of $0.97 \text{ mol}_{NH_3}/\text{kg}_{cat}/\text{h}$ was substantially lower compared to state-of-the-art Haber-Bosch synthesis at laboratory scale. However, the simulated productivity rate of a quasi-continuous SSR by Smith and Torrente-Murciano [7] was exceeded, which makes the case for the proposed dead-end operation mode. Nevertheless, an inherently transient process impedes the achievable space-time yield in an SSR. A sensitivity analysis regarding the operating conditions ($T_W = 540\text{--}590 \text{ K}$, relative catalyst volume 10%–90%, feed ratios of 0.5, 1.0 & 1.5) showed that operating the SSR at a temperature slightly below the hypothetical equilibrium temperature of the respective synthesis and sorption thermodynamic equilibria leads to the highest achievable NH₃ yield. Also, an increased amount of sorbent relative to catalyst material in the reactor appears favorable regarding NH₃ yield and productivity per catalyst mass, both due to an increased total sorption capacity and a decreased catalyst amount. An additional sensitivity study regarding sorption and synthesis kinetics (varied -80 to $+100\%$, relatively) indicates that an enhanced desorption kinetics would lead to an increased NH₃ yield, while the specific absorption capacity of NiCl₂ is principally invariable. Enhanced catalyst kinetics and a higher volumetric fraction of catalyst material, on the other hand, impede the single-pass ammonia yield as back-reaction in the presence of catalyst material during the desorption is favored.

At the same time, both sensitivity studies demonstrate the potential for performance optimization by adapting the operation recipe and the SSR design.

Hence, a logical extension of the presented dynamic modeling approach is the dynamic optimization (DO) of design and operation.

On the practical side, potential sources of limitations imposed by the involved materials (e.g., co-adsorption, poisoning and lacking material durability) so far remain unattended. Accordingly, the models developed herein can be validated on a pilot plant in the near future. Furthermore, additional catalyst and sorbent material combinations and different operating ranges can be investigated by means of the presented rigorous dynamic model.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

C. Sengoba: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization. **M. Illner:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **J.-U. Repke:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Operation recipe table

See Table A.4.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2025.110387>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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